

Investigation of antioxidant activity and isolation of bioactive constituents from *Albizia amara* bark extracts

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Abstract : Besides the achievements in the field of plant chemistry and drug development, there is still a burgeoning focus on the utility of pharmacological potential on the herbal diversity. With high impact of the above true lines, bark of *Albizia amara* [F : Fabaceae] was chosen to study its antioxidant activity. In a preliminary aspect, for the solvent extracts (hexane, ethyl acetate, acetone, methanol), the presence of useful constituents was screened to analyze its efficiencies through estimations like total phenolic, flavonoid contents, *in vitro* DPPH radical scavenging and reducing power assays using standard spectrophotometric analysis. Results of these assays proved that there were significant activities recorded by ethyl acetate fraction. Thus, through bioassay-guided fractionation, a phenolic acid was isolated, purified and characterized using spectral studies (UV, IR, ^1H and ^{13}C NMR, HR-MS). Furthermore, some topical biological applications for the compound were performed and have let the introduction of *Albizia amara* in the field of therapeutics.

Keywords : *Albizia amara*, DPPH, NMR, phenolics.

Introduction

The pharmaceutical experts consider the drug derivatives are vastly present in the plants species, rather than the clinical preparations, so as to solve the problems of side-effects, produced by the synthetic drugs. Rise in the population, increasing herbal consumer's adverse effects of synthetic, costly clinical treatments, newly discovered diseases etc., have led to the positive consumption of herbs. Pure constituents as isolated or the direct plant extract provides the chemists, an unlimited source on drug manufacturing supported by chemical diversity¹. These purified compounds being chemically active, have pharmacological properties and are widely submitted for clinical trials to demonstrate their synergistic potency. Hence, there is a world-wide competition in exploring novel compounds, which has a wide spectrum of biochemical properties especially active anti-tumor agents, anticarcinogenic, antioxidant, antidiabetic, antimicrobial activities etc.

With sufficient background, interwoven with above described, a traditional medicinal plant of India has been targeted to study their antioxidant efficiencies and plausible efforts to separate bioactive constituents. In line, *Albizia amara* has been excerpted to extrapolate its an-

tiioxidant properties especially on its bark. *Albizia amara* is used widely for leprosy diarrhea, leucoderma, erysipelas, gonorrhoea, abscesses, astringent etc.². Hence, the ultimate findings of this investigation would add to the existing knowledge on *Albizia amara*.

Results and discussion

Preliminary qualitative analysis of *Albizia amara* bark (hexane, ethyl acetate, acetone, methanol) extracts was conducted, using appropriate tests, which revealed the immense presence of active constituents like alkaloids, flavonoids, phenolics, steroids, tannin, saponins, glycosides etc. With the positive implication of this piece of analysis, valuable estimations have been performed. Significant phenolic contents was recorded by ethyl acetate fraction ($22.9 \pm 0.23 \mu\text{g}$) followed by methanol ($12.9 \pm 0.17 \mu\text{g}$) and acetone ($12.3 \pm 0.67 \mu\text{g}$). The least content was produced by hexane fraction of about $4.9 \pm 0.44 \mu\text{g}$ and the results are expressed in gallic acid equivalents. Likewise, richer flavonoid contents were observed in ethyl acetate fraction ($99.91 \pm 0.33 \mu\text{g}$). Surprisingly, next intense content was measured in hexane extract ($15.37 \pm 0.24 \mu\text{g}$) followed by acetone ($6.79 \pm 0.23 \mu\text{g}$) and methanol ($5.77 \pm 0.22 \mu\text{g}$) fractions. Their results are

expressed in catechin equivalents. From the above discussed estimations, it is evident that ethyl acetate fraction is capable of extracting intense phenolic and flavonoid compounds. In other words, the constituents of the plant consist of constituents matching to the polarity of the solvent ethyl acetate³. For a note, there were insignificant results provided by acetone and methanol fractions and served as a competence factor too.

In vitro biochemical antioxidant studies through DPPH-free radical scavenging and reducing property have shown the striking evidence for the application of *Albizia amara* bark extracts as safe antioxidant agents. In DPPH assay, it was observed that there was a steady increase in the %inhibition with the increasing concentrations of the extracts as depicted in Fig. 1A. This was the fact behind the DPPH radicals being scavenged efficiently (purple color of DPPH turning to pale yellow) by the ductants in the extracts. Thereby, almost all the extracts recorded their %RSA above 50%, in particular significant IC₅₀ value was measured in ethyl acetate with reference to the standard ascorbic acid. It is clear that this fraction containing intense amounts of phenolics and flavonoids has evidenced the strong ability to scavenge the free radicals. The increasing order obtained while analyzing the scavenging ability of various extracts, with respect to the IC₅₀ values were : ascorbic acid (0.132 mg) > ethyl acetate (0.156 mg) > methanol (0.165 mg) > acetone (0.222 mg) > hexane (1.661 mg).

Fig. 1B shows the reducing power capacity of the subjected extracts of *Albizia amara*. A steep increase in the absorption values with increasing concentration revealed the uniformity and systematic approach of this particular antioxidant assay. Noteworthy, IC₅₀ values were displayed by the ethyl acetate extract (0.092 mg) which was highly active compared with ascorbic acid (0.107 mg). But still as the concentration increased, the reducing power of the standard seems to stand one step ahead than the extract, besides their close competence. Next to ethyl acetate, it was methanol (0.118 mg) and acetone fractions (0.123 mg) being good reducing agents, hexane (0.149 mg) being the least significant. This activity has served as a proof that the extracts possessed phenolic or hydroxyl compounds to donate electrons to change Fe³⁺ to Fe²⁺.

An approach of bioassay-guided fractionation, ethyl acetate fraction is submitted for column chromatography, with renewing interest. A typical phenolic acid viz. vanillic acid was isolated, supported and justified by the supportive spectral data. It is mandatory to promote the biological activity of the plant isolated compound. Thus, antioxidant, antibacterial and antifungal activities were performed through *in vitro* basis. Antioxidant efficiencies analyzed using DPPH, peroxide radical scavenging activities and reducing power assay has produced excellent results. The IC₅₀ values obtained proves the 50% inhibition of the compound to scavenge the radicals and

Fig. 1. Various extracts of *Albizia amara* bark exhibiting (A) DPPH and (B) reducing power assay.

Fig. 2. Structure of 3-methoxy-4-hydroxy benzoic acid.

donate the electrons from its hydroxyl groups. Hence, the IC_{50} obtained at DPPH assay was 0.458 mg, hydrogen peroxide assay was 251 μ g and reducing power activity 0.999 mg, with comparison to the standard ascorbic acid. Moreover, antibacterial assays (zone of inhibition in mm) performed on strains like *Salmonella typhi* (18 mm), *Klebsiella aerogenes* (11 mm), *Enterococcus faecalis* (9 mm), *Cornye bacterium* (20 mm) and antifungal assays on strains like *Candida albicans* (16 mm), *Aspergillus niger* (9 mm), have demonstrated the inhibiting capacity of the compound at 40 μ g/ml.

Experimental

Authentication and extraction :

Plant : *Albizia amara* bark samples; Collected area : Mallur Forest, Salem Dt., Tamilnadu; Authentication : BSI/SRC/5/23/2012-13/Tech-586 by TNAU. Extraction : Sequential soxhlation using various solvents [*n*-hexane, ethyl acetate, acetone, methanol]; Storage : 4–5 °C.

Phytochemical screening :

Using standard methods³, the preliminary qualitative screening was analyzed for the presence of the secondary metabolites.

Estimation of phenolic content :

Estimated method : Standard procedures⁴ using Folin and Ciocalteu's phenol reagent; Absorbance range : 725 nm (Analytik Jena 200-2004 spectrophotometer). Standard : Gallic acid; Calculation : Standard curve at the range 0.01–0.4 mM, $Y = 2.94848x - 0.09211$, $R^2 = 0.99914$; Results expressed : μ g of gallic acid equivalents (GAEs) per mg of extract.

Estimation of flavonoid content :

Estimated method : Determined⁴ using aluminium chloride; Absorbance range : 510 nm (Analytik Jena 200-

2004 spectrophotometer). Standard : (+)-Catechin; Calculation : Standard curve at the range 0.250–2.500 mM, $Y = 0.2903$, $R^2 = 1.0000$; Results expressed : μ g of (+)-catechin equivalents (CEs) per mg of extract.

DPPH-radical scavenging study :

Concentration : 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0 mg/ml concentrations of *Albizia amara* extracts; Procedure : Spectrophotometrically assayed using methanol solution containing DPPH radicals; Absorbance range : 517 nm. Calculation : The radical scavenging activity - %RSA = $[(A_{DPPH} - A_S)/A_{DPPH}] \times 100$, where A_S is the absorbance of the sample extract and A_{DPPH} is the absorbance of the DPPH solution⁴. Standard : Ascorbic acid.

Reducing power study :

Concentration : 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 2.0 mg/ml concentrations of *Albizia amara* extracts; Procedure : Spectrophotometrically assayed⁴ by measuring the reduction system of Fe^{3+} to Fe^{2+} . Absorbance range : 700 nm. Standard : Ascorbic acid.

Hydrogen peroxide radical scavenging assay :

Concentration : 50, 100, 150, 200, 250 μ g/ml concentrations of *Albizia amara* extracts; Procedure : Spectrophotometrically assayed⁵ by measuring the ability of extracts to terminate the peroxide action. Absorbance range : 230 nm. Calculation : The radical scavenging activity - %RSA = $[(A_{Control} - A_S)/A_{Control}] \times 100$, where A_S is the absorbance of the sample extract and $A_{Control}$ is the absorbance of the solution containing peroxide free of extracts⁴. Standard : Ascorbic acid.

Antibacterial activity :

The activity of the compound at various concentrations (10, 20, 30, 40 μ g/ml) were performed against bacterial strains viz. *Salmonella typhi*, *Klebsiella aerogenes*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Cornye bacterium* using disc diffusion assay⁶.

Antifungal activity :

The activity of the compound at various concentrations (10, 20, 30, 40 μ g/ml) were performed against bacterial strains viz. *Candida albicans*, *Aspergillus niger* using agar diffusion assay⁶.

Isolation and characterization :

White amorphous material (80 : 20 ratio of hexane :

ethyl acetate), m.p. 206 °C; UV (λ_{max}) : 282 nm, (log ϵ) : 3.26; IR (ν_{max}) (cm^{-1}) : 3202 (COOH), 2850 (OH), 1680 (C=O), 1611 (C=C); HREI-MS m/z : 168.112 ($\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{O}_4$, calcd. 168.102) 168 (100), 151 (14), 123 (4), 97 (12); ^1H NMR (DMSO, 400 MHz) : δ 7.57 (1H, d, J 2.0 Hz, H-2), 7.12 (1H, d, J 8.2 Hz), 7.63–7.65 (1H, d, J 8.2 and 2.0 Hz), 3.88 (3H, s, OCH_3); ^{13}C NMR (MeOH-D4) : δ 55.7 (O- CH_3), 112.2 (C-2), 115.3 (C-5), 123.8 (C-1), 125.2 (C-6), 147.6 (C-3), 151.6 (C-4), 158.0 (COOH). The results are in agreement with the previous report⁷ and the compound has been identified as vanillic acid.

Statistical analysis :

All the above *in vitro* studies were experimented in triplets and the results calculated using one way are expressed as mean \pm SD using one way analysis (ANOVA).

Conclusion

From the results of the present investigation, it has become evident that *Albizia amara* bark has marked antioxidant property with proximate and chemical composition, especially its ethyl acetate fraction. Vanillic acid isolated from the plant has moderate antioxidant and an-

timicrobial properties and hence, *Albizia amara* bark shall be encouraged to explore its potential source to be applied on various diseases, so as to analyze the plant to display as significant drug candidates.

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References

1. D. J. Newman, G. M. Cragg and K. M. Snader, *J. Nat. Prod.*, 2000, **366**, 1022.
2. K. Kokila, S. Deepika Priyadharshini and V. Sujatha, *Int. J. Pharm. Pharm. Sci.*, 2013, **5**, 70.
3. G. E. Trease and W. C. A. Evans, *Pharmacognosy*, 1985, **12**, 394.
4. C. M. Barreira, C. F. R. Ferreira, M. Beatriz, P. P. Olliveira and Jose Alberto Pereira, *Food Chem.*, 2008, **107**, 1106.
5. R. J. Ruch, S. J. Cheng and J. E. Kalunig, *Carcinogen.*, 1989, **10**, 1003.
6. E. J. Threlfall, I. S. T. Fisher, L. Ward, H. Tschape and P. Gerner-Smidt, *Microb. Drug Resist.*, 1999, **5**, 195.
7. Z. Zhang, L. Liao, J. Moore, T. Wu and Z. Wang, *Food Chem.*, 2008, **113**, 160.